

The Effects of the Participation of Rural Residents to New Rural Construction in Viet Nam Red River Region

Author's Details:

(1)**Thi Phuong Thao Pham** (2)**Thuy Linh Tran** (3)**Mai Thanh Nong**

(1)(2)(3)University of Economics - Technology for Industries, Vietnam

Correspondence: Thi Phuong Thao Pham, 456 Minh Khai, Hai Ba Trung, Ha Noi

Abstract:

The participation of rural residents always plays a key role in building a new countryside, they are an important subject to implement many contents of NTM criteria. All commercial enterprise contents from planning, socio-economic infrastructure ... always need the active participation of rural residents to best meet the community's interests and legitimate aspirations of rural residents. At the same time, it can mobilize local resources to preserve the landscape, environment, natural ecosystems and the beauty of traditional rural areas (traditional culture, fine customs and traditions with cultural value. along with improving the material and spiritual life commensurate with the development of modern society through the sustainable implementation of NTM criteria with the highest quality

Keywords: Ural residents, new rural construction

1. Introduction

Around the world, participation is widely used in development theory and in development projects. In the late 1960s participation was mentioned in the areas of social or community development (Arnstein, 1969), later in the studies of community development and community work more and more mentioned. to public participation (Abbott, 1995). Participation helps socio-economic development programs, projects or plans to achieve their set goals in a more effective and sustainable manner; At the same time, it also affects the sharing of development benefits for stakeholders and supports management in the implementation process. On the other hand, participation also helps to rationally mobilize local resources for development (Chhetri, 2013).

In Vietnam, building a new countryside is a national target program that is widely deployed to implement Resolution 26 of the Central Executive Committee dated August 5, 2008 and the Government's Action Program to develop synchronously and comprehensively in rural areas in terms of economy, politics, culture and society, and preserve the ecological environment. After 9 years of implementation (2010 - July 30, 2019), the participation of rural residents in general and rural residents in the Red River Delta in particular has been increasingly evident at work. namely: enthusiastic comments, voluntary contributions of resources (money, material, land, workdays, ...); proactively and creatively in organizing production, improving rural livelihoods, enthusiastically participating in cultural and social development movements, maintaining security and order, ... places with active participation Rural households have actually increased the feasibility and sustainability of infrastructure works, good traditional culture has been preserved, the spirit of solidarity and attachment among the people has been promoted and Currently being responsible for the community, the village. In particular, the participation also helps to arouse the diligent nature, the inquisitive spirit, improve the dynamism of rural residents to help them develop more stable their family economy, upgrade houses, gardens, ponds, rivers, streams and fields create landscapes and make the countryside more spacious, clean and beautiful. The results of the commercial enterprise enterprise have achieved certain victories, mobilizing large resources in rural areas to develop relatively comprehensively in all areas of social life, the quality of life of the population. the countryside has been improved and improved, the forms of production organization in the countryside are increasingly renovated, the infrastructure is more and more modern and advanced, the natural landscape and environment are focused on better preservation to maintain and protect the ecosystem inherent in rural areas.

However, in reality, the implementation of commercial enterprises still has some shortcomings such as: running according to the criteria formally, the real quality of life of rural residents according to the new standards has

not been met or sustainable, in some places still over mobilizing people, a part of rural residents still do not understand the nature of the program, have not taken advantage of their advantages to rise, still have the thought of relying on support state investment. The participation in the implementation of criteria of income, production organization, environment and safety in production, trading and processing of agricultural products is still very limited and not really active, some households produce. Small and small businesses are unable to promptly respond to market fluctuations, epidemics, ... On the other hand, the need to upgrade criteria of NTMs (model NTMs) in the coming period is also a big challenge. the more active and proactive participation of the rural population.

2. Literature review

Firstly, the work outlines the concept and the meaning of participation

From the famous work of Arnstein (1969) on the ladder of public participation, later studies have shown that participation is always necessary for development in different areas of social life. These studies are based on the relationship of participation theory and the theory of stakeholders to draw out concepts of people's participation in each specific field (Latin American Economic Commission, 1973; UNDP, 1993; Nkunika, 1987; Lisk, 1980).

Later, works on participatory practice emphasized the meaning of participation in the use of local resources (Oakley, 1991), and the meaning of rural development organization (Oakley, 1995), meaning in creating trust and encouraging people to be more active (Richards, 2004).

In assessing the participation of the poor in sustainable livelihoods, some authors have cited the meaning of participation as key to "real and sustainable poverty reduction" through more empowerment of who are the "local and the poor" residents (Chambers, 1995; Nelson & Wright, 1995). Based on participatory practice in areas of social life such as education development (in the Philippines), infrastructure (Ha Tinh Vietnam, Sub-Saharan Africa) and forest management (Indian) shows how important participation is to help the poor increase their income and accumulate wealth. Since then, the World Bank has analyzed quite clearly the complexity of participation and made recommendations that it is necessary to encourage with specific actions that increase the voice of poor groups in coping with the social stratification or stigma. This implies that the mode of participation needs to be shaped in a broader institutional context (World bank, 2000). Other studies, demonstrate participation as a determinant of synchronous poverty reduction and rural development efforts (Chinsinga, 2003). Reasonable community participation is the key to sustainable development that the proposed development will be structured based on the needs and demands of stakeholders, including benefits. for future generations. Implementation of the public participation process is important to democratization of social values and for better planning and response to public needs. Participation is also useful for educating people on accountability in government development programs. This is what can affect social or personal changes among community members, which can be used to combine various public interests and thus allow everyone to have rights. participate in decisions that will affect their lives (Marzuki, 2015). Successful participation motivates people to be more active in jobs in the community and socio-economic development, while also increasing people's confidence in political decisions (Richards, 2004) .

Some studies on resources in developing countries show that most of these countries are still confused in finding ways to effectively use their resources, to overcome these limitations. need to rationally divide power to the locality, thereby increasing the accountability and initiative for the local government. The division of power should focus from reforming resource management to community participation for sustainable development (Manor, 1995; Verhagen, 1980; Mills et al., 1990; Ahmad, 2011). Citizen participation can ensure efficient use of available resources. If local resources (including human resources, resources, materials and finances) are used on the basis of decisions made by local people, that means participation must be performed. from the planning, decision-making, implementation and benefit-sharing phases of local people at their level. With the active participation of the local people, dependence can be disrupted and also to increase their awareness, confidence and focus on the development process (Nepal, 2009).

Second, research results discuss participation content

Participation content of rural residents is studied in different aspects of social life:

The results of community development studies have emphasized the content that encourages the participation of local people to increase the effectiveness of the project programs (Cleaver, 1999; Korten, 1980; Samah 2009; Marzuki, 2015; Malinga, 2017).

Studies on the theory of democracy, the content of the people can participate, are emphasized on the issue of political participation and participation in social management (Verba, 1995; Nguyen Trung Kien, 2012). The people's right to participate in social management is specified in the 2013 Constitution, Law on Promulgating Legal Documents in 2015, the Ordinance on the Implementation of Democracy in Communes, Wards and Towns in 2007. including: the right to participate in the discussion, monitoring and evaluation of activities and general affairs of the society (Article 28, Article 6, Article 36, Article 57, Article 10, Article 11).

In rural development, citizen participation focuses on rural economic development through the transfer of new technology to farming households (Chambers, 1995; Nelson & Wright, 1995; Cramb and Purcell, 2001; Cramb et al., 2004; Nwaobiala, 2014).

Third, the research results on modes of participation

In development theory, studies of community development and citizen participation appeared in the 1940s in the first British colonies from the very simple initiative of helping people improve their own lives. . The implementation process has in fact brought about a remarkable effect when the local people have actively contributed to improving their own lives. Later, the research on community participation is increasingly popular and studied in many different fields. In the area of regional planning and urban planning, how people participate in decision-making, people are informed by democracy, input into planning and decision-making (Chadwick , 1971). Studying the participatory approach, the authors demonstrate community participation as a means of communicating the personal interests and concerns of society in relation to development plans, These planning activities will subsequently affect the general community and specific groups (Slocum et al., 1995; Marzuki, 2015).

The mode of citizen participation in community issues is calculated from planning to decision making and then evaluation (Rifkin et al., 2002). In follow-up studies, the modes of public participation are also explained by the authors as the processes by which public concerns, needs and values are incorporated into the decision-making process. Citizen participation takes place in many different areas such as civil society, elections, legislation, and administration and can take many forms and methods to participate from information exchange to decision making. The core value for the practice of public participation is stated by the International Association for Public Participation: (1) people need to take the initiative in decisions that affect their lives; (2) Participation includes the contribution of resources to the organization of decision implementation; (3) People's participation makes decisions feasible and sustainable because the needs and interests of all stakeholders are guaranteed in the decision; (4) Participation helps to find and facilitate the participation of those potentially affected by the decision; (5) Participation aims to seek input from participants in the design of how they participate; (6) the engagement process that helps inform stakeholders so that they can participate in a meaningful way; (7) People's participation helps them understand how their participation influences the decision (IAP2, 2006).

Fourth, research results on factors affecting participation

However, participation is not always the same everywhere. In the Human Development Report (UNDP, 1993), the factors that can affect the participation of rural residents are: health, knowledge, skills and social norms, individuals This factor has limited their participation. In the study of social exclusion, many authors have demonstrated that lack or inability to participate in important areas of society, the multidimensional aspects of poverty affect participation (Hills et al, 2002; Dorsner, 2004). Researches on forest management show that

literacy and gender factors affect the participation of residents in forest management and conservation projects (Lise, 2000). Studies in tourism development, which have shown that understanding the details of projects and understanding the importance of ecotourism or community engagement also influence participation of residents in tourism development projects (Briedenhann et al., 2004; Lee, 2013). Further studying culture, Cornwall (2003, 2008), Nuttavuthisit (2015) demonstrate that cultural values, norms, responsibilities, competence and inexperience are important barriers that can affect participation of residents. Rural residents' awareness also influences their participation (Long, 2009; Besculides, 2002; Wang, 2008).

The author Xuefeng introduces the concept of the new countryside of China on the basis of research in the aspect of building social culture, improving rural lifestyles and increasing benefits for farmers, and thereby helping farmers. people against the negative effects of the market economy. New rural construction focuses on socio-cultural construction to make the countryside a place of economic and social stability as well as a strong rural foundation for China's modernization (Xuefeng, 2007).

Some other works, when researching on issues related to new rural construction, agreed to use the concept of a new countryside on the basis of the criteria set for a new countryside. Since then, the author has studied the practice to explain each of these factors (Long et al., 2009) and analyze the factors affecting the process of building a new countryside (Long et al., 2010).

Research on new rural areas in Vietnam, author Vu Trong Khai cited scientific bases on the basis of traditional rural analysis and new rural economic development models to introduce new rural concepts. In addition, the new countryside is also viewed from two aspects: (i) "Changing thinking about rural areas is an important value of the new rural movement". To do this, it is necessary to arouse the spirit of patriotism, self-control and self-reliance to rise up in every farmer. At the same time, state management agencies also need to play their leading role through creating a driving force for rural development, improving residents' lives, building a rich healthy cultural and spiritual life. maintaining national identity, creating stability and democracy, helping people to be confident in their lives; (ii) Agriculture should be considered as the core of rural development. Change in policy mechanisms, institutional reforms to make appropriate investments and promote effective investment attraction in agriculture and rural areas to create sustainable growth for agriculture, increase the competitiveness of products. agricultural products to adapt to the deepening international economic integration and the increasingly complex capacity to withstand the risks posed by climate change (Dang Kim Son, 2016).

The doctoral thesis in Agricultural economics by Nguyen Mau Thai (2015) from the practice of building NTMs in the western communes and districts of Hanoi City has argued the concept of building a new countryside in terms of economic, political, cultural, social and environmental aspects in rural areas aim to improve the quality of life of rural people, develop harmoniously, shorten the gap between urban and rural areas. The process of building NTMs as the subject of rural people with active support from the State and other organizations. The author conception that a new countryside and building a new countryside is: (i) Ensuring a comprehensive rural development not only economically, but also in terms of politics, culture, society and environment; (ii) Ensure immediate but stable and sustainable development in the long term; (iii) The goals of building a new countryside are increasingly completed but specific goals must be achieved in each stage.

On the other hand, from the practice of building a new countryside in coastal China, the author Long et al (2009) also draw out the meaning of enterprise trade to help protect agricultural land and build "clean villages and neat ". Agricultural land protection policies have been strictly applied, although agricultural land has been reduced but used effectively to improve the living conditions of villagers, according to the author, this is also an important factor to help improve production. and ensure national food security, avoid wasting land resources. The second meaning mentioned in his work is that the Enterprise Trade makes the village clean and tidy in terms of: expanding the use of clean fuels (methane and solar energy) in rural areas, Rural households have standard sanitation facilities, gradually improving their rural housing according to the village planning in a scientific and strategic way.

Later, Chen (2012) argued that the most effective way to reduce rural poverty is to develop depressed areas and build new rural areas. According to him: Building a new countryside is a guide to rural poverty reduction through development in the new period; The key to poverty reduction in rural areas is to increase the participation of rural people themselves to promote their own ability to develop themselves out of poverty; Particularly strong interest in economic development; unify programs and projects to promote harmonious development in poor areas.

The author's research determines the participation of local people From the practice of building NTMs in China, author Long et al. (2010) analyzed the effects on commercial enterprises in China and outlined the internal Participation of farmers includes participation in planning, making decisions and implementing them; while the government is responsible for planning and providing public infrastructure and services; Social organizations can act as a partnership. Meanwhile, research by Yansui (2011) shows that the participation of rural residents in new rural construction is to improve production conditions, increase income; improving the living conditions of rural residents through promoting the self-reliance of the people instead of government aid, from which the author proposes to change policy priorities, ensuring farmers play a role. pillar role and scientific construction "Rules of building a new countryside".

Author Li (2014) studies on building a new countryside in the aspect of rural landscape construction with the aim of improving rural life and protecting the regional culture and rural ecological landscape. From the theory and practice of rural landscape, the author has made a statement: the protection of the rural landscape and its ecological resources has become a prerequisite for new rural construction. , the landscape mentioned by the author includes the natural landscape and architectural works, topography, space, cultural and historical characteristics of each rural area.

The author Looney (2015) argues that farmers 'mindset changes towards: The Government should only play a supporting role for the Farmers' Union; Farmer participation should encourage even more empowerment, but there is always a need to create mechanisms and control the implementation; At the same time, the author has analyzed the changes in rural areas and demonstrated the mode of participation of rural residents in improving their livelihoods and came to the conclusion that if this method is well implemented by residents, the criteria In terms of economy, raising income in new rural construction will fulfill the set target and more and more suitable and better livelihoods will appear in rural areas.

Factors affecting the participation of rural residents in new rural construction

Research by author Nguyen Van Tuan on the reality of implementing commercial enterprises in Vietnam in a specific commune (Thuy Huong commune) with the assumption that the level of people's willingness to contribute (the dependent variable) depends. In the following factors: people are widely propagated = X1, people clearly understand the meaning of the target of the program XDNTM = X2, people are allowed to participate in discussing the planning of the program = X3, the people understand the investment for each item = X5, people understand the content of the new rural criteria = X6, people are allowed to participate in the inspection and supervision of the implementation of each item = X7 (variable independently), the author has tested by exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to identify the influencing factors and the level of influence of each factor on the people's willingness to contribute. for the vocational training program, after testing Cronbach Alpha and EFA, the author regression to determine the relationship between the level of people's willingness to contribute to the chapter XDNTM process with results: increasing by 1 point in each of the above independent variables, the dependent variable increases respectively: 0.29, 0.395, 0.176, 0.021, 0.175, 0.018 and 0.022. Since then, the author draws 5 lessons from experience that the planning is the premise, the propaganda must be clear about the content, the implementation organization must be synchronous and democratic, strictly managed, the commercial enterprise must synchronize ministries in all aspects of social life, interested in training and fostering grassroots cadres (Nguyen Van Tuan, 2012).

Researching from the perspective of psychology, author Le Thi Thanh Huong and colleagues analyze the psychological factors of farmers that affect their participation in 3 aspects: Propaganda: content, ways propaganda mode affects the psychology of participation of people; The results of commercial vocational training in localities affect their psychology of participation. The contents of new rural construction have clearly improved the life and practical benefits of rural residents, promoting their active participation; Community activities: when stakeholders have positive interactions, agree on the implementation, sharing the community's common interests will promote the participation of each member (Le Thi Thanh Huong, 2015). Pham Huynh Minh Hung's Ph.D. thesis in Philosophy (2017), in addition to studying the subject role of farmers, the author goes into depth analysis of 5 factors that affect the promotion of the subject role of farmers in Commercial enterprises are: domestic and foreign socio-economic conditions, grassroots political system, the policies of the Party - State policies, farmers' awareness level, psychological and social factors.

3. Research method

a. Approach

The thesis has used the following main weighting methods:

- Access to policies and institutions: Through the study of guidelines and policies related to the participation of rural residents in building a new countryside.
- Participatory approach: Participatory research, exchange, investigation of households, managers ... to collect and evaluate the participation of rural residents in construction. build a new countryside.
- Territorial approach: Research on the participation of rural residents in new rural construction is conducted in different territories in the RRD, focusing on communes where rural construction has been conducted. new with the purpose of understanding the similarities and differences about the participation of rural residents in commercial enterprises among regions.

b. Analytical framework

Inheriting the scales of participation from previous studies, combined with direct interviews with organizational experts, implementing a new rural construction program (Chairman or Vice Chairman of the Commune People's Committee) and households In the family, the author inherits the mode of participation of rural residents that the previous studies mentioned to apply to the study of rural residents' participation in the implementation of criteria for commercial enterprise registration and the relationship between People's participation with commercial enterprise results

The author uses research data from two sources: Secondary data is collected from published documents such as: reports, previous research results, data of agencies, organizations, statistics yearbook, magazines, internet,...; Primary data from in-depth interviews, conducted in the form of semi-structured interviews with full closed-ended and open-ended questions, i.e. the interview is developed based on a list of questions required for the study. Research has been designed already, but during the interview, you can change the order of questions and how to ask questions depending on the context in the interview; Time for each interview takes place from 30-45 minutes. Through the interview process, the author introduces new ideas and findings from previous interviews into the next interview and finally, new findings are used by the author for data analysis. The author stops interviewing when not.

Based on the list of households and the suggestion of the commune leader, the author has selected the head of household over 18 years old, understand Vietnamese and can take the time to answer the questionnaire. The author chooses to combine the form of sending the questionnaire at home, making an appointment for the time to return the questionnaire and the form of sending the questionnaire by mail to the house (with the cost of sending the courier) to not take a long time of households. With the self-filling questionnaire set up, the

collected information is quite complete and the response rate is high, meeting the expected requirement for 384 questionnaires.

From the documents and data collected, the thesis uses SPSS software (software to support primary data processing and analysis) to process data for analysis.

- Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics are used to analyze the current situation of rural residents' participation in the construction of new rural areas in the Red River Delta from 2010 to July 30, 2019. This method is used to describe and analyze collected data in the form of tables and charts to give an overview of the current state of participation of rural residents in the Red River Delta in general and household groups in 5 surveyed communes. in particular.

On that basis, it proposed objectives and proposed solutions to promote the participation of rural residents in commercial enterprises in the Red River Delta.

Comparative statistics

Comparative statistics are used to analyze the comparative evaluation of participation among rural residents, regulators and between regions to clarify the role and impact of participation. to the result of new rural construction.

- Testing the quality of the scale

The survey model has 6 independent groups of factors measuring the participation of rural residents with 24 observed variables, and 01 dependent factor measuring the results of new rural construction with 4 observed variables. Cronbach Alpha method is used to assess the reliability of the scale, the results of running Cronbach's Alpha have 7 scales to ensure good quality with 28 characteristic variables (Appendix 1), in which: Cronbach's Alpha value of the Representative variables are both greater than 0.6 and less than 0.95, so the scale questions have no duplication in measurement, proving that these scales are of good quality.

4. Research results

Table 1. KMO results

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.680
Approx. Chi-Square	2893.502
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity df	210
Sig.	.000

Durbin-Watson test results of the regression model are as follows

Model (Mô hình)	R	R Square (R ²)	Adjusted R Square (hiệu chỉnh)	Std. Error of the Estimate (Sai số chuẩn ước lượng)	Change Statistics (Thống kê)				Durbin-Watson
					F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
1	.525 ^a	.276	.262	.85903515	20.430	7	376	.000	1.298

Although the communes meeting the new rural standards have actively propagated, mobilized and organized to comply with regulations, there are still some households that have not actively participated (the number of households participating at the average level or less still accounts for about Twenty percent depending on the content and each criterion, ...), even some households just follow the majority of households who have done (passive participation).

There are still households who perceive that landscape and environmental sanitation is too simple, so they are not regular and proactive in implementing the criteria. There are households that do not classify waste so they burn plastic waste without knowing the danger, first of all, their own health, then the surrounding environment, ... Or there are households who still think about implementing the criteria. Landscape, the environment is the responsibility of the local government so when there is a strong deployment, do it, then take it lightly ...

5. Conclusion

Participation in collective organizations is one of the trends to help disadvantaged people build collective strength to adapt to a deeply integrated economy. In the commercial enterprise collective activities of the residential community and social organizations in many localities have made great contributions to the process of commercial enterprise registration, the collective has helped their members overcome difficulties, they have mobilized rural residents actively participate in village / hamlet infrastructure development; helping each other develop economic and self-managed in environmental sanitation, ... Participation in collective organizations in rural areas such as cooperative groups and cooperatives helps farmers to act together to improve their livelihoods. Concentrating land to expand production scale to improve sustainable livelihoods, linking production to give them better access to safe inputs, advanced production technologies and techniques. to ensure food safety, protect the ecosystem, protect the environment and be more proactive in product consumption, ... Therefore, local authorities need to have appropriate management measures and guidance. , creating favorable conditions to help residential communities and social organizations to perform well the self-management role in implementing NTMs criteria in accordance with law. In particular, there should be a mechanism to encourage farmers to participate in collective economic organizations, agricultural enterprises in rural areas to better implement the economic criteria and organize production in a sustainable direction. to develop more and more modernly in accordance with local advantages and development trends of international economic integration. Local governments need to effectively implement the Government's Decree No. 98/2018 / ND-CP dated July 5, 2018, on encouraging the development of cooperation and association in production and consumption of agricultural products; In which, attention should be paid to the direct stakeholders that create agricultural products, namely farmers; Need to encourage, propagate and do well the role of state management to increase the accountability of stakeholders to form collective action in participating in collective organizations to effectively implement linkages. follow the value chain of sustainable agricultural production, processing and consumption, and widely apply science and technology to reduce costs, improve agricultural value, and increase the competitiveness of agricultural products.

Market development for rural agricultural and industrial products is one of the next jobs to support the process of improving more sustainable and effective livelihoods. However, this is the weakness of rural residents, most of them do not have knowledge about the market or agricultural product processing industry. Therefore, in addition to guiding and implementing the "economy and production organization" criterion, the authorities at all levels need to play a key role in developing markets for agricultural products, agricultural products and promoting Rural residents participate in training courses on market knowledge to help them distinguish more clearly the duality of the market economy, what do they need to do to understand correctly and actively expand the market. schools consume their own agricultural products, ...

Conferences

- i. Abbott. J (1995), 'Community participation and its relationship to Community Development', *Community Development Journal*, 30 (2), pp. 158-168.
- ii. Ahmad. S. M and Talib. A. N Bt (2011), 'Decentralization and Participatory Rural Development: A Literature Review', *Contemporary economics*, 5 (4), 58-67.
- iii. Ameha. A., et al (2014), 'Impacts of access and benefit sharing on livelihoods and forest: Case of participatory forest management in Ethiopia', *Ecological Economics*, 97, pp. 162 - 171.

- iv. Aref. F (2011), 'Farmers' participation in agricultural development: The case of Fars province, Iran', *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 4 (2), 155-158.
- v. Arnstein. S. R (1969), 'A ladder of citizen participation', *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35(4), pp. 216 - 224.
- vi. Aylett. A (2010), 'Participatory planning, justice, and climate change in Durban, South Africa', *Environment and Planning A*, 42, pp. 99-115.
- vii. Bachmann. L. P., et al (2007), 'Analysis of the citizen's participation concept used by local decision makers: the case of the Aysén watershed in southern Chile', *Int. J. Sustainable Development*, 3 (10), pp. 251-266.
- viii. Chen. Y, Lu. B and Chen. R (2016), 'Evaluating the life satisfaction of peasants in concentrated residential areas of Nanjing, China: A fuzzy approach', *Habitat International*, 53, 556-568.
- ix. Chhetri. P. D (2013), 'People's Participation in Development: Sikkim in Perspective', *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 2 (5), pp. 1477-1497.
- x. Chinsinga. B (2003), 'The participatory development approach under a microscope: the case of the poverty alleviation programme in Malawi', *Journal of Social Development in Africa*, 18 (No 1), pp. 129-144.
- xi. Choguill. G. B. M (1996), 'A Ladder of Community Participation for Underdeveloped Countries', *Habitat intl*, 20 (3), pp. 431-444.
- xii. Cleaver. F (1999), 'Paradoxes of participation: questioning participatory approaches to development', *Journal of International Development*, 11, 597-612.
- xiii. Conrad. C. C and Hilchey. G. K (2011), 'A review of citizen science and community-based Environmental monitoring: issues and opportunities', *Environ Monit Assess*, 176, 273-291.
- xiv. Cramb. A. R, Purcell. T and Ho. S. C. T (2004), 'Participatory assessment of rural livelihoods in the Central Highlands of Vietnam', *Agricultural Systems*, 81, 255-272.
- xv. Cramb. R and Purcell. T (2001), 'How to Monitor and Evaluate Impacts of Participatory Research Projects: A Case Study of the Forages for Smallholders Project', *CIAT Working Document*, 185.
- xvi. Danielsen. F., et al (2009), 'Local Participation in Natural Resource Monitoring: A Characterization of Approaches', *Conservation Biology*, 23(1), pp. 31-42.
- xvii. IAP2 (2006), 'Techniques for effective Public Participation', pp 06.
- xviii. Karl. F (2000), 'Principle of Participation for open Information Community', *Crime and Delinquency*, 46(2), 147-155.
- xix. Kelly. K (1995), 'Evaluating participation processes in community development', *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 18(4), pp. 371 - 383.
- xx. Khamung. R (2015), 'A Study of Cultural Heritage and Sustainable Agriculture Conservation as a Means to Develop Rural Farms as Agritourism Destinations', *Silpakorn University Journal of Social Sciences, Humanities, and Arts*, 15(3), 1-35.
- xxi. Korten. D. C (1980), 'Community Organization and Rural Developmen: A Learning Process Approach', *Public Admimistration Review*, 40 (No 5), pp. 480 - 511.
- xxii. Laah. D. E, Adefila. O. J, and Yusuf. O. R (2013), 'Community Participation in Sustainable Rural Infrastructural Development in Riyom Area, Plateau State of Nigeria', *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4, 19.
- xxiii. Looney. E. K (2015), 'China's Campaign to Build a New Socialist Countryside: Village Modernization, Peasant Councils, and the Ganzhou Model of Rural Development', *The China Quarterly*, 224, pp. 909-932.
- xxiv. Mak. L. K. B (2017), 'Community Participation in the Decision-Making Process for Sustainable Tourism Development in Rural Areas of Hong Kong, China', *Sustainability*, 9, pp. 1-13.
- xxv. Malinga. W (2017), 'Decentralisation and Rural Development: Is it a Policy of Empowering or Disempowering Rural Communities in Zimbabwe?', *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 6(4), 132-143.

- xxvi. Manor. J (1995), 'Democratic decentralization in Africa and Asia', *IDS Bulletin*, 26 (2), 81-88.
- xxvii. Marzuki. A (2015), 'Challenges in the Public Participation and the Decision Making Process', *Sociologija I Prostor*, 201 (1): pp. 21-39, <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org>.
- xxviii. Mather. S. A, Hill. G, and Nijnik. M (2006), 'Post-productivism and rural land use: cul de sac or challenge For theorization?', *Journal of Rural Studies*, 22, 441-455.
- xxix. Mathur. N. V, Price. F. D A, Austin. S and Moobela. C (2007), 'Defining, identifying and mapping stakeholders in the assessment of urban sustainability', *International Conference on Whole Life Urban Sustainability and its Assessment*, Glasgow, Scotland.
- xxx. Njoh. J. A (2011), 'Municipal councils, international NGOs and citizen participation in public infrastructure development in rural settlements in Cameroon', *Habitat International*, 35, pp. 101 - 110.
- xxxi. Nkunika. Z. I. A (1987), 'The Role of Popular Participation in Programmes of Social Development', *Journal of Social Development in Africa*, 2, 17-28.
- xxxii. Nurlaila. I, Yuliar. S, Kombaitanb. B and Madyo. E. A (2015), 'Public Participation: Energy policy aspect to support rural electrification program in West Java', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 168, 321-327.
- xxxiii. Nwaobiala C. U, Ogbonna. M. O and Egbutah. E. U (2014), 'Assessing Levels of Participation among Farmers in IFAD/Fgn/NDDC/Community-Based Natural Resource Management Programme in Abia and Cross River States, Nigeria', *Discourse Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences*, 2(5): 136-141.
- xxxiv. Oakley. P (1989), 'Community involvement in health development', *World Health Organization Geneva*.
- xxxv. Oakley. P (1995), 'People's Participation in development Projects: A critical review of current theory and practice', *Intrac Occasional Papers Series 7*, Oxford.
- xxxvi. Oakley. P., et al, (1991), 'Projects with people: The practice of participation in rural development', *International Labour Office, Geneva*.
- xxxvii. Park. S (2009), 'Analysis of Saemaul Undong: A Korean rural development programme in the 1970s', *Asia-Pacific Development Journal*, 16(2), pp. 112-140.
- xxxviii. World Bank (2000), *World Development Report 2000/2001 - Attacking poverty*, Oxford University Press.
- xxxix. Xiande. L (2003), 'Rethinking the peasant burden: evidence from a Chinese village', *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 30, pp. 45 - 74.
- xl. Xuefeng. H (2007), 'New Rural Construction and the Chinese Path', *Chinese Sociology And Anthropology*, 39 (4), pp. 26-38.
- xli. Yansui. L, Yangfen. C and Hualou. L (2011), 'Regional diversity of peasant household response to new countryside construction based on field survey in eastern coastal China', *Journal of Geographical Sciences*, 21(5), pp. 869-881.
- xlii. Ye, J. and H. Fu (2015), 'Peasant Innovation and Grassroots Action in China, In Constructing a New Framework for Rural Development', *Research in Rural Sociology and Development*, 22, pp. 89 - 126.
- xliii. Zomorrodian. A. H, Gill. S. S, Samaha. A. A, and Ahmad. N (2013), 'Quantitative Models for Participation Evaluation in Community Development: A Theoretical Review', *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 25(2), 314-322.